

NPT Post-Module Evaluation Survey

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Course Title
Intake Survey

Intro Thank you for taking the time to participate in this survey. Your responses will assist the Nevada Partnership for Training in evaluating current performance and identifying areas for future improvement. All responses are confidential.

Q15 If you are completing this survey on your phone, be sure to rotate to landscape mode.

Q1

Curriculum Effectiveness Please indicate the degree to which you disagree or agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. The curriculum was easy to follow.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. The training materials (i.e., handouts, audio-visual materials, workbooks, learning aids, etc.) supported my learning of the training content.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. The training provided opportunities to apply concepts through classroom activities and discussion.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. The pacing of the training allowed me to remember and understand the content.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q2

Trainer Effectiveness Please indicate the degree to which you disagree or agree with the following statements:

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
5. The facilitator was knowledgeable regarding the subject matter.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. The facilitator helped connect content to real-world child welfare practice.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. The facilitator presented the content of the training clearly and effectively.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. The facilitator encouraged participation and engagement.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. The facilitator created a respectful and inclusive learning environment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q3

Level of Understanding

	None	Slightly Knowledgeable	Somewhat Knowledgeable	Considerably Knowledgeable	Extremely Knowledgeable
10. What was your level of understanding of this topic PRIOR to the training?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. What is your level of understanding NOW?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q4

Overall

	Very Poor	Poor	Fair	Good	Excellent
12. How would you rate this training as a whole?	<input type="radio"/>				

Q5 13. Please provide any feedback, suggestions, or comments you have regarding the training.

End of Block: Default Question Block